

Social Rights Of The Individual In The Social State and State Obligations

Dr. Aynur SARAN (0000-0002-6343-503X),

Assoc. Prof. Kürşat Şahin YILDIRIMER (0000-0001-5896-2956),

To cite this article: Collaborate, Science, Volume 5, No. 2-5, 2023, p. 24 – 44. - 0099-0001-2302-0404.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

""• *Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic*"" (*"CURRENT SCIENCE A Different Look at Traffic Sociology and Driver ..."*) (*"Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia"*) (*"Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia"*)

journal with a multi-science peer-review." (*"Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia"*) (*"Scientific Studies -*

Current Science Georgia")

""*The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month.*"" (*"Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia"*)

• *The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this* (*"Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia"*)

""• *Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.*"" (*"Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia"*)

Abstract

The state, which is a structure that is above and beyond other institutions, is an entity that encompasses a whole nation's society and brings its people together under a single set of goals. According to Aristotle's interpretation of this scenario, the primary function of the state is to provide "good life" and "common benefit" for its citizens, and it is this function that pulls people closer together. When we talk about the "common good," we're referring to the realization of social justice. When we talk about "good living," we're referring to

the improvement of the citizens' standard of life, as well as the equitable distribution of income and exercise of rights.

Nineteenth and XX Century The well-being of the people who make up a society has evolved through the ages to become the primary focus in the meaning of the term "social state," which was formed for the aim of achieving this goal. This understanding, which found it necessary for the state to intervene in social and economic life, therefore aimed to provide a minimum level of living to the powerless. In this context, the aim was to ensure that each individual gets a share from the national income, which would ensure social justice and social balance. It is generally agreed that the "social rights" that evolved as a consequence of the establishment of the social state are the "rights to demand" that govern the duties of the state towards people and the demands that persons may make of the state. One of the most significant of these demands is to insist on the social state adhering to the ideal of guaranteeing social justice in all of its policies and practices. Only by enforcing policies of "fair wage" and "fair tax," that is, by adhering to the ideals of "equal compensation for equal effort" and "everyone pays taxes according to their financial power," can the state deliver social justice to its residents. This is the only way that social justice can be achieved. In this piece of research, an attempt will be made to explain the concept of a social state, as well as the rights of the person inside a social state and the responsibilities of the state toward its inhabitants.

Key words: *Social State, Social Rights, Social Justice, Fair Pay, Fair Tax*

1. Introduction

In the year BC, the "state," also known as a supra-institutional framework, was established. In 5000 BC, the Sumerians in Mesopotamia gave rise to an extended their city-states across the region. Later BC. According to Goze (2017), beginning in the eighth century and continuing forward, it developed into a political, social, military, and economic entity that included one or more towns named "Pôlis" in Ancient Greece.

Throughout the course of history, people's need for safety and the requirements that generate the requirement of a social life have combined to establish the foundation of such an organization. These organic wholes, which were brought together by organizing to achieve a "common and good existence," finished their growth by passing through various political administrations in both the eastern and western parts of the globe. This was done to complete their development. Later, kingdoms and aristocratic administrations took the place of police and city-states, and during this transition, democratic governments emerged. Throughout these phases of transition, the concept of "law and order" in the Roman Empire started to become institutionalized as the primary organizational principle of the state phenomena. Developed a structure for organization that was founded on a comprehension of law and order. Following the collapse of the great empires, there was a shift in both the "feudal state structure" and the concept of the state. At the same time, there was a growing reliance on individuals, which led to the development of the nation-state form, which was first formalized in the Treaty of Westphalia in 1648. has been initiated. (Dursun, 2018).

- *Definition of the State*

"State" is an abstract concept, it is the largest and most developed political institutions, and it is the most inclusive one because it contains many organizations and institutions (Daver, 1975). As a result, the state is formed by the combination of many institutions with distinct functions, duties, and authorities, and it is itself a combination of those institutions. It is an organization that does not have a higher authority than the rest of its members and brings everyone together under a single will (Kapani, 2000).

According to Meray (1960), a community is defined as "a social organization equipped with a political organization whose purpose is to ensure social order, justice, and the welfare of the society, owning a community of people settled and living on a certain piece of land, exercising legitimate authority on this land." State: "It is a social organization equipped with a political organization whose purpose is to ensure social order, justice, and the welfare of the society"

One of the most fundamental characteristics that sets the state apart from other types of organizations and institutions is its exclusive right to exercise lawful power, sometimes

known as the use of coercion and violence (Dursun, 2018). The "government," also known as political power, is the entity that has the authority to employ the power of the state to preserve social order inside the state. To be fair, however, is the most crucial element throughout the process of establishing social order, and ensuring that public authorities carry out their responsibilities within the bounds of justice is equally essential. People will continue to respect their state only to the degree that they believe that they are being treated fairly; otherwise, contradictions may form in the society, and it may grow into a chaotic order despite the fact that it is sought to construct an order (Oztekin, 2016).

When the definitions of the state are examined, it can be seen that these definitions have developed around two main axes; the first of these is the view that accepts the state as an absolutely abstract and transcendent value, and the second of these is the view that sees the state as a tool of liberal and utilitarian philosophy in its modern sense. XVII in its modern sense. Plato's view of what he called the "ideal state" in the XIX century served as the inspiration for the transcendent state understanding of the state, which was an institution that did not exist until the 19th century. In the 19th century, it was deified and reached its zenith with the "Hegelian Philosophy," and the "liberal view" of the state was revealed as an institution based on the protection of society and social life, as well as the performance of the necessary functions in order to continue in an orderly fashion (Dursun, 2018). As a consequence of this, the state is an entity that possesses qualities such as compulsory membership of citizens, the power to punish legally and legitimately, the ability to provide its own organizations and formations, that is created by human logic and actions, and most importantly, that has its own "legal personality." In addition to having the greatest sanction power, the state is an entity that possesses qualities such as compulsory membership of citizens, the power to punish legally and legitimately, that can provide its own organizations and formations, and that is created by is a person or thing with legal standing (Okandan, 1976).

2. Social State

Social state; It is a state model that originated inside the liberal state's own structure in order to enhance the social welfare of the society. This model's name derives from the term "social state." In order to achieve this goal and to maximize the level of social welfare, the state intervenes in the functioning of social and economic life. This means that it takes measures to eliminate the problems that cause poverty, injustice in income distribution, and therefore a decrease in the level of social welfare. In this perspective, the interventionist, regulating, redistributive, entrepreneurial, and granting rights and freedoms to people are all beneficial aspects of the social state (Aktan, 1995).

Liberal state XX. This phase of capitalism, which was completed in the second half of the century, is substantially the same as the second half of the system as a whole. According to Yilmaz (2006), the country had progressed to this point by the 1950s, following the end of World War II.

XIX. The emergence of social problems and inequalities in the first half of the century because of the emergence of different income groups in parallel with the development of the industrial revolution caused unrest in the society, which resulted in the need to eliminate these tensions and ensure social balance. This need emerged because of the fact that the industrial revolution occurred simultaneously with the emergence of different income groups. The concept that the liberal economic order was unable to live up to the aspirations of society and that the inflexible capitalism that was formed because of the industrial revolution upended the social structure was the impetus for social conflicts and increased social awareness. The idea of a "social state" was conceived by several philosophers in response to the battles that were taking place.

The concept of a "welfare state," which was coined by Archbishop Joseph Temple in 1941, refers to a model of the state that interferes with the natural flow of market forces. It was built on a fundamental idea that envisions the support of people by offering them social and economic rights to guarantee that they may live without falling below a standard level of life. This fundamental understanding was the basis upon which it was established. In addition to this, it has been implemented in order to broaden the scope of economic liberty

enjoyed by all participants in the society, to bring about social equity and justice, and to strengthen the bonds of social cohesion and solidarity.

In a social state, the individual is both the source and the purpose of both society and the state, and the objective of the state is to serve the individual by catering to his material and spiritual needs as well as fostering his growth as a person overall. In this context, the individual; It is in opposition to totalitarian and authoritarian behaviors that consider it as a weapon at the disposal of society and the state (Goze, 2017); hence, social state does not imply socialist state. It is a functioning organism that lives in a given social and economic context, has social ties, and is active in socio-economic and political organizations. Humans in their social condition; These institutions, which are crucial and required for the person's growth on both a material and spiritual level, are at the service of the individual in the same way as the state is. In addition to the liberties and rights that were established by the revolution of 1789 in the social state, "social rights" were acknowledged as a result of the fact that countries, particularly I. and II. Following the wars, people began to realize that the traditional freedoms alone were not enough to ensure the happiness of a society. In order for there to be peace in a society, its members must have the economic opportunity and social rights necessary to fulfill their fundamental need.

Because social rights are a triumph of respect for human dignity and justice, human freedom and dignity, the provisions on social rights adopted in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights have become the rules of law in the constitutions of all states today. This is because social rights were adopted as part of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

Following the events of the French Revolution in 1789, the state was given the responsibility of "raising abandoned children and finding jobs for the unemployed" under the Constitution of 1791. Additionally, under the Constitution of 1793, the state was required to "provide public aid to the poor citizens" and "to provide education to all citizens." In 1848, the responsibilities of the state toward people were expanded, and the state was given the mandate to "defend persons, their families, beliefs, property, and labor; provide education; and assist the crippled and the aged without money." Later, not only were provisions for social rights written into the founding documents of many nations, but there were also

significant advances made with the passage of the "New Deal" legislation in the United States in 1933 and the "Beveridge Plan" in England in 1943. In Turkey, the "Social State" structure and the notion of "social rights" were both established with the adoption of the 1961 Constitution, which was followed by the adoption of the 1982 Constitution, which maintained this stance (Goze, 2017). state" started to become less important over time.

Gasta Esping-Andersen analyzed the welfare state in three categories.

a) Liberal Social State: Market logic is dominant in the state, so it is possible to ensure welfare through the market. USA, England, Australia and New Zealand are among the countries in this category (Özdemir, 2007)

b) Conservative Social State: While importance is given to market efficiency, the right to social security is provided to those who do not work. France, Germany, Italy, Austria and Belgium are included in this category (Akgül Yılmaz, 2006)

c) Social Democratic Social State: It is based on the principle of "Ensuring the equality of individuals in having the Highest Standards", universality, social solidarity and equality are prioritized. Sweden, Norway, Denmark and Finland are in this category (Aktan, Özkıvrak, 2008).

The aims of the welfare state in the literature:

- *Guaranteeing a minimum level of income to individuals*
- *Ensuring minimum standards in meeting their needs*
- *Improving the living conditions of all individuals in the country*
- *Ensuring fair income distribution by fighting poverty*
- *Ensuring social justice*
- *Providing social protection and social security provision*
- *It has been determined as making basic individual rights and freedoms functional by strengthening them with social and economic rights and freedoms.*

The social state uses many tools by developing various policies to achieve these goals . These policies are; It is examined as “economic policies” and “social policies”:

a) Economic Policy

It includes both the making of choices by the state in order to attain its goals and the subsequent carrying out of those decisions. When the government becomes involved in the economy, it employs the instruments of monetary and credit policy, finance, international trade, regulatory and controls policies, and (SEE) State Economic Enterprise policies (Aktan, 1993).

b) Social Policy

It encompasses the actions done by the state to safeguard the economically vulnerable, the needy, and the destitute, as well as the provision of a service with the goals of economically enhancing the condition of workers, assuring the people' futures, and increasing the degree of societal wellbeing. The instruments that the state use to implement this policy are referred to as social insurance, social incentives, social benefits, and social recompense (Tokol, 2000).

By using these policy tools, it has developed, the state:

- *It aims to provide justice in the distribution of income and to fight poverty, in this context; • In order to prevent inequalities in income level by using public revenues, it tries to reduce the imbalances by redistributing income from the rich to the poor and to develop methods of protecting weak, destitute, and needy children who need to be brought up and taken care of (Aktan & Ozkivrak, 2008). • In this context, it aims to provide justice in the distribution of income.*
- *It aims to eliminate full employment and unemployment; It provides the conditions for individuals to find a job and obtain a job.*

• • *In this context, it seeks to establish a life order worthy of human dignity and individuality for everyone. This includes governmental rules, the individual, disease, accident, old age, and other stages of life. It protects him against every conceivable risk in the hopes of ensuring that he will always have at least some amount of income available to him.*

• • *The provision of economic growth and development is the primary function of the social state. In order to fulfill this function, the state creates the environment and conditions required for an increase in production, incentivizes financial investments, and regulates economic activities. This, in turn, allows for full employment (Aktan, 1993).*

• *It seeks to accomplish these objectives in order to improve the social equilibrium, peace, and welfare of the community. These goals should be considered the primary goals of any social policy. Since the concept of a social state presupposes the involvement of the state in aspects of social and economic life and, in this context, the provision of chances for living lives that are inherently healthier, more convenient, and more just for those who are disadvantaged (Aktan, 1998).*

All of them are made possible by the social state, which relies on social rights. This explanation informs us; therefore, what does the notion of “right” entail, and who are the people who are entitled to social rights?

1. What is right, what does it mean?

“It relates to the interests of individuals judged worthy of protection by the legal system,” says one definition of the idea of right, which makes it one of the most significant and basic notions in law. It often falls into two categories: public and private rights. TDK. “The circumstance that persons demand or allot to someone by the law is characterized as a lucrative scenario,” reads the definition of profitable situation provided by the dictionary. Consequently, the idea of “right” is connected to individuals; if there is a person, there is also a right; the right belongs exclusively to the person; yet, the fact that a person has a right

demonstrates that other people also have the same rights. Because people have fundamental, natural rights that they only have because they were created as human beings, that they are innate and cannot be given up or transferred, there can be no privileges observed between people in terms of rights in an egalitarian society (Güngör, 1997), because these rights are innate and cannot be given up or transferred. These rights, which are generally acknowledged to be “human rights,” are a collection of social rules that apply to everyone everywhere. In this sense, rights originate from the concept that individuals should be shielded from all forms of tyranny and slaying due to the inherent worth they hold in society. The requirement of a person not being exploited as a tool in any manner, shape, or form, together with their equality with other individuals in terms of human rights, is how the worth of a person is communicated (Gedik, 2003). The field of philosophical anthropology, which is concerned with the worth of humans in general, articulates this value in terms of human occurrences that may be traced back to a biopsychic existence (Gedik, 2003). In point of fact, the idea of “justice” may be found nested inside the notion of “right,” which Plato discussed in his dialogues included within the book “The State.” According to Plato, the concept of right exposes the meaning of “anything owing to someone,” and in the context of human rights, it provides the definition of “things that all individuals one by one owe to all other people” (Gedik, 2003). According to who holds them, human rights may be broken down into two categories: fundamental human rights and citizenship rights.

Personal Rights That Are Fundamental: It addresses the “inviolability and liberties of the person” and asks that individuals’ ability to exercise their rights not be impeded in any way. Citizenship rights are the rights that a person obtains as a result of being a citizen of a nation. These rights may be formed via the social, economic, and political rights that are recognized by the state, as well as through other institutions and organizations. The state must fulfill its responsibility to safeguard these rights (Kucuradi, 1988). The human being is an entity whose worth is intrinsic in itself, and as such, the human person is the root of both society and the state (Ozcan, 2016). The meaning of life is only conceivable with human beings, and life only gets meaning with the presence of human beings (Ozcan, 2016). (Soykan, 2019).

For this reason, human rights are aspirational rights that have been outlined in international declarations and treaties for many nations, but are not guaranteed in most countries (Oztekin, 2016). Human rights have been called “wishy-washy rights.” Aspects constituting human rights:

- *Human rights are universal*
- *They are inalienable and unconditional rights.*
- *They are fundamental innate rights simply by virtue of being human.*
- *They are rights that can be asserted against everyone.*
- *must be protected by law*
- *These are unlistable rights due to their dynamic nature (Bozkurt, 2018)*

2. Who are social rights for? Definition of social rights

The social circumstances that emerged because of industrial giants showed the reality that individuals were not truly free. This was notably evident in the poverty of the “working class,” which demonstrated that members of this class did not have adequate enjoyment of their human rights. The principle of the “social state” that emerged in this environment laid the groundwork for the establishment and development of rights for the less advantaged members of society and provided them with the means to live in a manner that was commensurate with human dignity. These rights have been established and developed for the purpose of allowing these individuals to live their lives with human dignity (Bulut, 2019). In this regard, social rights, which are also referred to as “rights to demand” in many diverse sources, are defined as “the rights that make it possible for the individual to demand certain things and certain attitudes from society and its organized form, the state” (Ruhi, 2013). In this regard, social rights are defined as “the rights that make it possible for the individual to demand certain things and certain attitudes from society and its organized form, the state.” In addition, while it is defined as “the rights for the protection of economically and socially weak and needing protection – women,

children, and families, and in this respect, the state's undertaking some duties in this regard" (Goze, 2005), it is also defined as "the rights for the protection of economically and socially weak and needing protection." Kaboglu also provides a description of his own definition regarding the topic, which reads as follows: "Social rights are the rights that can be realized by the positive intervention of the state in the form of taking measures or taking direct actions so that the weaker sections of the society can lead a life worthy of human dignity" (Ruhi, 2003).

Individuals are entitled to social rights when the state is required to take a positive action as a result of those rights being exercised. As was said before, the origin of both the society and the state in a social state can be traced back to the human element, which is one of the primary components that comprise the states and also serves as the source of the social state. One key distinction is that under the social state, in addition to the person, the social institutions created by the individual, most notably the family, serve as the foundation of society (Goze, 2017).

- *individual and citizen*

"Each of the individuals who make up the societies and whose intellectual, emotional, and volitional attributes are determined inside the society, as an individual," is how the word "person" is used in TDK. People are referred to be "citizens" if they belong to the same state in which they reside and share a physical address inside that state. Citizenship is the term used to describe the legal connection that exists between natural individuals and the state in which they live. Citizenship obligations may be regulated by states, provided that such regulation does not violate fundamental human rights. Marshall citizenship, named after the well-known British sociologist who first coined the term, is defined as "a condition including the introduction of various rights and powers."

The presumption of equality is singled out as the single most crucial component of importance in this assertion. Marshall maintains that all contributing members of a society have the same responsibilities and rights.

In this scenario, the citizen of the social state is a person who has "social rights" since they are the source and purpose of the state. The Constitution of Turkey from 1982, which is a social state of law, provides the rationale for this practice. The Constitution states that "Social rights are not an economic philosophy, but rather, first and foremost, the result of humanism and humanity's sense of fairness." It is the natural and even unavoidable effect of valuing human dignity and acknowledging the person as a holy being, while Article 5 of the Constitution from 1982 also stipulates that "The state will aid the individual's battle for life." The person will live in a setting that is appropriate for the maintenance of human dignity. This is the responsibility that falls on the state... It is the primary responsibility of the social state to eliminate the impediments that stand in the way of individuals exercising their rights and freedoms within the parameters set by the social state. The social state respects the human and human rights of thinking. II. After World War II, western democracies came to terms with the concept of the "social state," and as a result, social rights were written into the constitutions of those countries in greater detail.

It becomes clear that the idea of social rights imposes certain debts on the state when it is seen as a request from the state for citizens to do particular acts. As a result, the state is obligated to act and, thus, to "do." Constitutions often include clauses that protect citizens' social and economic rights:

- 1) *Protection of the family*
- 2) *The right to education and training*
- 3) *Right to work*
- 4) *Collective bargaining agreement*
- 5) *Ensuring fair wages*
- 6) *Right to health*
- 7) *Environment and right to housing*
- 8) *Right to social security*

- 9) *Consumer rights*
- 10) *Protection of youth and the right to sport*
- 11) *The right to protect historical, cultural and natural assets*
- 12) *Protection of agriculture and livestock*
- 13) *It is stated as the regulation of working life.*

These social rights are often referred to as "duties placed on the state" in contemporary constitutions. The obligation of the state to provide the essential circumstances for its inhabitants results in the establishment of "rights to claim" for those persons. However, these social rights are not universal; rather, each state recognizes social rights to the extent that its power permits, namely; The priorities of the countries are planned by making a profit and loss calculation, because the social and economic rights that are actually required to be realized are limited to the realities of the country; Regardless of the circumstances, the governments of the country must realize both the economic development of the country and social rights simultaneously (Goze, 2017). The right to work, the right to education, the right to health, the right to environment and housing, and the rights to protection of the family will all function properly with a brief explanation if we consider the social rights and duties of the state in modern constitutions (Goze, 422-423 and 424). Since these rights are both a human right and a social right, they are referred to as dual rights.

- *Right to work*

The right to work in a social state is one of the most important rights of individuals, which cannot be given up. This right entitles individuals to a job, a decent living, and a minimum standard of living for themselves and their family and dependents. The protection of this right is an obligation of the state. For this state:

- *It should create sufficient employment opportunities,*

- *It should improve the quality of manpower with the education policies it will develop.*
- *It should act as an intermediary between job seekers and job seekers,*
- *Job security and protective standards should be applied,*
- *Wage guarantee should be provided,*
- *Employees should take measures to ensure occupational health and safety.*
- *Employees should be given union rights,*
- *It should ensure that employees are protected against unemployment (Koray, 2005).*

Individuals not only have the right to work, but also the freedom to "work in any job they like." [Case in point] Nobody can be coerced into doing labor that they do not wish to perform. Period. The freedom to work is an important component that goes hand in hand with the right to work. When a person exercises his or her freedom within the bounds of the law, the state has no right to interfere with or prohibit that individual from exercising that freedom.

It is the responsibility of the state to ensure that its workers receive their full pay and benefits, that they are not forced into jobs that are inappropriate for their age, gender, or physical ability, and that they are given the opportunity to improve their standard of living. In addition to rescuing people from poverty, the state has other responsibilities toward its workers, including the following: ensuring that workers take their paid vacations, holidays, and other time off when it is their turn; ensuring that workers take their paid time off when it is their turn. In addition to this, it is obligated to provide things like assistance (Goze, 2017). Martyrs, disabled and veterans of war and duty, widows and orphans, the disabled, the elderly, and children in need of protection are all included under the social security umbrella (Goze, 2017). While the state is thus regulating business and working life, to establish the necessary organizations in the context of the "Social Security

rights" of the employees and to take measures to ensure this security, as well as those in need of special protection;

- *Education right*

Education is referred to be a "process of modifying behavior" or a "process of constrained acculturation" since it allows for the growth of an individual's capabilities. While education is a process, it is also a goal that should be pursued since it contributes to the growth and peace of society. The purpose of education is to teach individuals how to acquire the knowledge they will need throughout their lives by building on the skills they currently possess in order to better prepare them for the world that lies ahead. It is a basic right as well as a social right, which speaks to the significance of this right. "Every individual has the right to education," according to the International Declaration of Human Rights. Free education is provided up to the elementary and secondary levels of education. Because education not only increases respect for the protection of human personality and dignity, fundamental human rights, freedoms, and peace, but also develops critical thinking, creative thinking, and questioning skills, it is considered as a prerequisite for many human rights in many international documents. This is because education not only increases the respect for the protection of human personality and dignity, basic human rights, freedoms, and peace (Altunya, 1997).

In terms of education, a social state is obligated to offer the circumstances that will assist its residents in materially and spiritually developing, and as a result, it is responsible for meeting the education and training requirements of its citizens. It is the government's responsibility to ensure that every individual, regardless of their socioeconomic standing, has access to the financial resources necessary to further their education to the greatest possible level so that they may further improve their skills (Goze, 2017). In regard to this topic, the state;

- *Educational Institutions should open*
- *Needed teachers and instructors should be trained*

- *Inspect, supervise and audit*
- *Scholarships should be given to students with limited financial means.*
- *Dormitories should be opened to meet the need for shelter.*
- *Developing measures for individuals who need special education and have hearing, speech and learning difficulties and reintegrate them into society.*
- *These studies should be presented openly to everyone with an understanding of equality and equal opportunity.*
- *No individual should be able to receive services without discrimination in accessing opportunities.*

- **Right to Health**

The concept of a social state refers to a government that strives to provide its residents with both material and moral support, to improve their overall level of life, and to implement policies that are respectful of their rights. In this regard, it guarantees that its duties stemming from these rights are fulfilled by making social expenditures using public resources, which helps it meet its commitments (Claphom, 2010).

The social state has taken on the responsibility of ensuring that all its people attain a level of human dignity and are able to maintain their bodily and mental well-being throughout their lives. In this context, it will primarily provide social security to this group of mothers, children, young people, disabled people, elderly people, and people who are unable to work. This will be done to save them from the fears of the future and to provide them with shelter in accordance with the conditions of their health. Therefore, the social state will protect both the present and the future of its citizens, fulfill their obligations to prepare the conditions that will enable them to continue their lives despite occupational, physiological, and socio-economic risks, and continue their lives as healthy individuals. In addition, the social state will fulfill its obligations to ensure that its citizens fulfill their obligations to prepare the conditions that will enable them to continue their lives as

healthy individuals. The "right to health," which is included both in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights as a human right and in the constitutions of the countries that ratified the declaration as a fundamental right, has been regulated as the right of every individual to have the highest possible physical and mental health standards as an extension of the right to life. This right is included both in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights as a human right and in the constitutions of the countries that ratified the declaration. The countries that ratified the declaration are the Furthermore, it is expressly stated that it is a right (www.saglikhakki.org).

Everyone should be able to lead their life in mental and physical health, everyone should be able to access health services equally and fairly, and the state should fulfill this duty by planning a national health policy, through legal practices, through health and social institutions, and to support the "right to life," which is the most important right. is required to contribute. In accordance with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights; Everyone should lead their life in mental and physical health; Everyone should be able to access health services equally and fairly; Everyone should be The question therefore is, what should the social state do to provide for them?

- *First of all, vaccination programs against infectious diseases should be implemented.*
- *Health services that prioritize the treatment of the people in case of illness should be provided.*
- *It should be ensured that citizens have access to nutritious and safe food, and economic measures should be taken in this regard.*
- *Obstacles to citizens' access to clean drinking water and meeting their mandatory sanitation needs should be removed.*
- *In order for citizens to live in a balanced and healthy environment, suitable housing and living conditions should be provided.*
- *Adequate doctors and medical personnel should be trained.*

- *Barriers to medical education and the best education and training of medical personnel should be removed.*
- *A sufficient number of hospitals, clinics and health-related immovables should be spread across the country in an equitable manner.*
- *Measures against harmful substances that impair health and their use should be followed meticulously, deterrent measures should be developed, campaigns should be organized, and the younger generation should be directed towards sports.*
- *Most importantly, sufficient economic opportunities should be provided to the citizens of the country so that they can attain a good job, live in healthy shelters, eat healthy, provide a good education for their children, take a vacation, have a social security where they do not worry about their future, and, in a nutshell, live in a manner that is befitting of human dignity and in a healthy manner. Complementing individual liberties and ensuring that those liberties are accessible to all people (Goze, 2017). Social rights that will be provided and implemented so that every individual can benefit equally from economic freedoms, meet their essential needs, develop their material and spiritual existence, and live in a humane manner.*

- ***Environment and Housing Right***

- *Housing*

To be able to live in a dwelling that satisfies certain health requirements and to be given the chance to do so is one of the requirements for persons to live in a way that is commensurate with the human dignity that is owed to them. Because the right to shelter is one of the most natural fundamental rights of the individual (Kabolu, 1996), and because, as of today, all of the first, second, and third generation rights, specifically the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and all of these rights expressed in similar international documents, are included in the scope of human rights, and because the right

to shelter is one of the most natural fundamental rights of the individual (Kabolu, 1996), and because the right to shelter is one of the most natural fundamental rights of the (Kapani, 1993). The right to a healthy environment as well as the right to a healthy household are intertwined with a substantial number of other rights. To be more specific, the right to life, the right to health care, the right to education, and the right to education are all intimately connected to an individual's ability to cultivate both the material and spiritual aspects of his or her identity and existence. In the Universal Declaration of Human Rights from 1948, it states that "there is an absolute equality between the economic, political, civil, cultural, or social rights, and all of these rights have the same importance." In addition to emphasizing that it is not possible to separate the rights of the people, we can understand this from the expression "there is an absolute equality between the economic, political, civil, cultural, or social rights," which states that "all of these rights have the same importance" (Turhan, 2013).

Within the context of "taking measures to meet the housing needs" for its citizens and the scope of the right to live in housing that is appropriate for health conditions, one of the constitutional obligations of the social state is to support mass housing enterprises. This obligation falls under the heading of "taking measures to meet the housing needs."

- Environment: It is the physical and biological environment in which all living things interact and continue to interact throughout their whole lives. It is also the environment that was formed by creatures that developed as a result of the presence of living things on earth. This environment, which is often referred to as the natural environment, is one that exists naturally and is unaffected by the actions of human people.

The environment is the place in which living creatures are able to survive. Apart from this, the surroundings that were developed as a result of human interference should also be referred to as artificial environments. One of the rights referred to as "Third Generation rights" is the right to the environment. These rights highlight the fact that future generations also have the right to profit from the current environment. It is connected to the most fundamental human right, sometimes known as the "right to life," as well as the "right to develop a person's material and spiritual existence." In addition,

everyone has the right to live in an environment that is both healthy and well-balanced, since this contributes to both a person's physical and mental well-being. More specifically and specifically, this right implies that individuals are able to breathe clean air, have access to clean water, have sufficient food to be nourished both physically and economically, and do not live in an environment that poses a risk to their lives. The social condition, understood in this context;

- *Make plans that take into account the characteristics of living spaces and environmental conditions.*
- *Measures and measures should be developed for people to live in a healthy environment and healthy housing.*
- *The safety of the living environment must be ensured*
- *Measures should be taken and controls should be tightened about waste materials that cause damage to the environment and cause diseases to live, causing changes in the natural characteristics of plants and other living things, thus causing genetic deterioration.*
- *Measures should be developed to prevent chemical contamination of drinking water basins, forest areas and agricultural areas.*
- *Every citizen's right to live in an environment suitable for living and their duties in this regard should be included in the education curriculum, and young Individuals need to have their consciousness elevated.*
- *In 1972, the United Nations for the first time acknowledged that people had a right to the environment. It was first included in the Stockholm Declaration that was published by the Environment Commission, and then it was presented at the Rio Conference in 1992. After that, it was included into the constitutions of the respective countries.*

- ***Right to Protection of the Family***

A fundamental aspect of human dignity is the right to a secure and stable family life.

Since the family is the most fundamental unit of healthy societies and the most natural environment for the growth and well-being of children, this right has an indispensable relevance for all areas of human rights. In this regard, the duty for ensuring the safety of the family falls not only on society but also on the state (tihek.gov.tr). Family is the foundation of society (Aktürk, 2008), so in this context; Due to its social roles, social position, and function, it has been included in many international documents, and arrangements have been made to protect the family (Şimşek, 1992). In this way, the family has been recognized as an important social institution.

Article 16 of the European Social Charter, which was signed on October 18, 1961, is titled "The right of the family to social, legal, and economic protection." This article states that "The contracting parties undertake to improve the economic, legal, and social protection of family life by means of Social Assistance and family benefits, financial arrangements, housing, assistance to newlyweds and other means, in order to provide the necessary conditions for the full development of the family, the basic unit of society." The European Social Charter was signed on October 18, 1961. According to Akıllıoğlu (1995), this regulation is also a prerequisite for adhering to the social state premise. While meeting these commitments, social giants are obligated to act in accordance with the concept of "social justice" and to take the steps required to eradicate "social injustice."

- **What is Social Justice?**

In the context of each person's right to a life worthy of human dignity, social justice can be expressed as receiving one's fair share of the national income and ensuring that every segment of society reaches a level at which they are able to maintain their economic life. This is an essential component of the right to a life worthy of human dignity. It provides a life guarantee at certain standards, a happy life in which trust, and justice are provided, in order to provide equality of opportunity to all members of the

society without harming the freedoms they have because they are human, and to save people from poverty. In this sense, the purpose of providing social justice; human; (Ruhi, 2003). Therefore, social justice is the regulation of social relations between the individual, who is a member of the society, and the society, in order to realize the common good, and the equitable distribution of blessings and burdens within the society (<https://www.egitimsistem.com>>adal... Access 18.06.2022). It is feasible for people to live without falling below a standard living level as a result of the state's interference in social and economic life and its goal to achieve social balance via such interference. This makes it possible for the state to adjust its functioning. What is indicated by the term "intervention" in this context is that the state takes on the responsibility of social duties and ensures that it will satisfy the fundamental requirements of people who are unable to obtain an adequate portion of the national revenue. Under this framework, the concept of the social state has been embraced with the expectation that it would foster social unity and solidarity, expand economic liberties, and guarantee social equality and justice (<https://turkmedeniyet.org>>bit...)

In order to realize social justice in the social state, it is necessary, first and foremost, to establish a fair division of labor as well as a fair wage policy; a merit-based social order must be established in assignments; the rights of workers must be determined and protected; it is necessary to support working life and create an economic environment that is favorable; this is because the economic balance of societies is what determines whether or not social justice is realized in the social state. When it is disrupted, the state of social harmony deteriorates as well. As a result of the "social justice" theory in the social state being built around the idea of the person, the principle of equal citizenship has been implemented in place of discrimination based on sectarian affiliation and gender.

The development of a "middle class" within a society is essential for the achievement of social justice. This is due to the fact that the benefits accruing from production should be distributed across the population to the greatest extent possible, and that social differentiation should be minimized as a result (Akyol, 2017; <http://turkmedeniyet.org>>bir...) (Akyol, 2017).

- **Policies that ensure social justice:**

- *The right to fair wages; It is a right that demands the wage, which is the equivalent of the labor, to be proportional to the effort spent, to be at a level sufficient to provide for the individual's livelihood, and to be paid more than the normal wage in case of overwork (Bulut, 2003).*
- *The right to equal pay also demands that the wages paid to one worker be paid equally to other workers doing work of the same value, regardless of race, gender, or nationality.*
- *Determining the minimum wage is one of the most important obligations of the state within the scope of the right to fair wages. The minimum wage should be in accordance with the principle of the social state that the employee should be able to make a living under minimum conditions, and if it is not appropriate, the feature of this wage to provide assurance to individuals cannot be mentioned (Bulut, 2003).*

As a requirement of social justice;

- *Tax Policy*

The implementation of the redistributive function of the national income is greatly dependent on the fiscal policy that is in place. In this context, the social state is a state with a tax habit, and the groups that are the source of the taxes collected by the state are also an essential element that determines the social character of the state (Güclü, 2007). Tax is an activity that is aimed at providing social balance and reducing the tension between social classes, according to Kara (2004). In this context, the social state is a state with a tax habit. Since the taxation system in contemporary governments is based on the principle of "taking more from those who make more and less from those who earn less," as a result, "every person pays taxes according to his financial power" (Ruhi, 2003). This idea guarantees societal peace and calm by creating social balance, which lowers the disparity between social classes and, as a result, the tension that exists between them.

3. Conclusion

The social condition of the nineteenth century began to take shape in the industrialized nations of the West at the end of the twentieth century. Up until the final part of the century, it spread at an alarming rate. Throughout the course of global history, wars, economic depressions, and natural calamities have not only altered the trajectory of the globe, but they have also altered the responsibilities that are placed on governments. As a direct consequence of this, the "social state" paradigm was proposed. social state; It is a model of state that aims to increase the welfare level of the society that fights poverty and injustice in income distribution by interfering with the functioning of social and economic life, specifically market forces, in order to optimize the social welfare of its citizens. This model of state aims to increase the welfare level of the society by fighting poverty and injustice in income distribution. It has been shaped on the premise of its residents being able to live without falling below a basic level of life, and in this context, providing them with social and economic rights. The concept of a social state has been formed on the basis of this idea.

Based on this understanding of the social state, to ensure that individuals have equal access to opportunities in order to make their equality before the law more effective; to develop measures to prevent poverty by providing justice in the distribution of income; to eliminate unemployment by providing full employment; and to increase production in order to ensure the growth and development of the country in order to ensure that individuals can live a life that is worthy of human dignity. As such, it makes public rules in an effort to satisfy its responsibilities in this regard. It does both by making sure that the minimum wage and tax release are equitable in the society; this avoids social injustice and makes sure that social peace and calm are maintained; this brings about social balance.

4. Resources

- Akıntürk, T. (2008), Family Law, Beta Publishing House, Istanbul
- Aktan, CC (1993), From Public Economy to Market Economy: Privatization, Tokav Printing House, Ankara
- Aktan, CC ., (1995), Optimal State Towards a New State Model for the 21st Century, Recommendations for Restructuring and Downsizing of Public Economy and Administration, TUSIAD Publications, Istanbul
- Aktan, CC and Özkıvrak, Ö. (2008), Social Welfare State, Okutan Publications, Istanbul
- Akyol, A. (2017), Social Justice in Individual and Social Life, (<http://turkmedeniyet.org>bir> ...) Access 19.06.2022
- Altunya, N. (1997), A Bird's Eye View of Our Educational Problems, Product Publications, Ankara
- Bozkurt, E. (2018), International Human Rights Law, Asil Publishing House, Ankara
- Bulut, N. (2009), Social Rights from Industrial Revolution to Globalization, XII. Plate Publications, Istanbul
- Claphom, A. (2010), Human Rights, (Trans. H. Gür), Dost Publishing House, Ankara
- Daver, B. , (1975), Introduction to Political Science, Ankara University. Faculty of Political Sciences Publications, Ankara
- Dursun, D. (2018), Political Science, Beta Publishing and Distribution Inc. , Istanbul
- Gedik, NY (2003), “Ioanna Kucuradin's View of Human Rights”, *Uludag University Journal*, 2 (2): 12-19
- Göze, A. (2005), Liberal, Marxist, Fascist, National Socialist and Social State, Beta Publications, Istanbul
- Göze, A. (2017), Political Thoughts and Administrations, Beta Publishing Inc. , Istanbul

- Güçlü, F. (2007), Tax and Social State, Sobev Publications, Ankara
- Güngör, E. (1997), Moral Psychology and Social Ethics, Ötüken Publications, Istanbul
- Kaboglu, I.O. (1996), The Right to Settlement and Housing: Fundamental Freedom and Social Rights Unification, Human Rights Yearbook, C.17 Issue: 1
- Kapani, M. (1993), Public Freedoms, Yetkin Publications 7th Edition, Ankara
- Kapani, M. (2000), Introduction to Political Science, Bilgi Publishing House, Ankara
- Kara, U. (2004), The Rise and Fall of the Social State, Özgür University Library, Ankara
- Koray, M. (2005), Social Policy, Image Publications, Ankara
- Kucurradi, I. (1988), Uludağ Speeches, Turkish Philosophy Society publications, Ankara
- Meray, S. , (1960), Introduction to International Law, Ankara University Faculty of Political Sciences Publications, Ankara
- Okandan, RG (1976), General Public Law, The Birth of the State, Its Positive and Theoretical Development, Elements, Istanbul University Press, Istanbul
- Özcan, M. (2016), Human Philosophy, Bilgesu Publishing, Ankara
- Özdemir, S. (2007), Welfare State in the Process of Globalization, Istanbul Chamber of Commerce Publications, Istanbul.
- Öztekin, A. (2016), Introduction to Political Science, Siyasal Publishing House, Ankara
- Ruhi, ME (2003), Social State and Privatization in the Framework of the 1982 Constitution, Atlas Publishing, Istanbul
- Sallan, Gul, S. (2004), Social State is Over, Long Live the Market !, Ethics Publications, Istanbul
- Şimşek, O. (1992), “Protection of the Family in terms of Constitutional Law”, Dokuz Eylül University Department (Unpublished Master's Thesis), İzmir
- Smartoğlu, T. (1995), International Basic Documents on the Protection of Human Rights, Bilgi Publishing House, Ankara

- Soykan, O.N. (2019), *Philosophical Landscapes from Turkey*, Bilge Culture and Art, Istanbul
- Tokol, A. (2000), *Social Policy*, Rota Ofset Printing and Packaging Industry. Inc. , Bursa
- Turhan, A. (2013), “The Complementary Relationship Between Human Rights Generations”, *İnönü University Faculty of Law Journal* , 4 (2).
- Yılmaz, GA (2006), *Social State and Social Expenditures in OECD Countries and Turkey*, Arıkan Publications, Istanbul